

NOTES

filtered hot. The yellow solid left was recrystallised from glacial acetic acid and was identified to be coumarin-3-carboxy (3-chloro-2-methoxy) anilide (A) m.p. 238°, yield 0.94 g (58.02%).

(Found : C, 62.20% ; H, 3.88% ; N, 4.51% ; Cl, 10.56% ; Calcd. for $C_{17}H_{12}O_4NCl$; C, 61.91% ; H, 3.64% ; N, 4.24% ; Cl, 10.77%).

The ethanolic extract was concentrated and on cooling gave 0.32 g (25%) of 2-hydroxy benzal (3-chloro-2-methoxy) aniline (B), m.p. 54°.

(Found : C, 65.00% ; H, 5.15% ; N, 5.26% ; Cl, 13.48% ; Calcd. for $C_{14}H_{12}O_2NCl$, C, 64.24% ; H, 4.58% ; N, 5.35% ; Cl, 13.57%).

The identity of this product was further confirmed by synthesising an authentic specimen from 3-chloro-2-methoxy aniline and salicylaldehyde.

The substituted salicylaldehydes were condensed with different malon anilic acids in the same manner and the product extracted as described above. The effect of different condensing agents was also studied. The coumarins and Schiff's bases obtained along with their analytical results m.p. are recorded in the Table 1.

Antibacterial and Antifungal Activity Test :

Some of the coumarins and Schiff's bases synthesised have been tested for their antibacterial and antifungal activity "in vitro".

It was found that 6-bromo-coumarin-*o*-phenetide was active against the bacteria *B. subtilis* (activity = 6.25 r/ml), and the fungi *T. mentagrophytes* (activity = 50 r/ml), *A. niger* (activity = 50 r/ml), 6-chloro-coumarin-3-carboxy (3-chloro-2-methyl) anilide active against the bacteria *S. aureus* (activity = 12.5 r/ml), *B. subtilis* (activity = 6.25 r/ml) and the fungi *A. niger* (activity = 50 r/ml), 6 : 8-dibromo-coumarin-3-carboxy (3-chloro-2-methoxy) anilide active against the bacteria *V. comma* (activity = 200 r/ml) and the fungi *T. rubrum* (activity = 200 r/ml) and 5-chloro-2-hydroxy-benzal-2'-aminothiazole active against the fungi *C. albicans* (activity = 200 r/ml) and the rest of the compounds were found to be inactive.

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Chemical Constituents of *Psidium guava* Heartwood

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THE wood of *Psidium guava* tree, although not an important timber, is still used for making some instruments specially spear handles; the stem bark of this plant has been worked up in the past for its polyphenols¹.

The shavings of the heartwood were extracted with boiling ethanol and the concentrated extract fractionated into (I) light petrol, (II) ether and (III) ethylacetate soluble fractions. Fractions I and II furnished β -sitosterol, m.p. 138° and gallic acid, m.p. 253° (dec), along with small amount of quercetin respectively, which were identified by comparison (ir, mmp and Co-TLC) with authentic samples. Fraction (III) was a mixture of three compounds. This fraction on concentration and standing at low temperature for a few days, deposited white shining crystals, m.p. 308°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 76^\circ$ (CHCl₃). This gave positive colour reactions for triterpenoids, formed monoacetate m.p. 266°, and insoluble salt with KOH and methylester m.p. 198°. This was finally confirmed as oleanolic acid by superimposable ir spectrum and undepressed mmp with an authentic sample. The mother liquor after removal of oleanolic acid was chromatographed over silica gel column to give two compounds. One of these, a buff coloured semicrystalline solid on boiling with ethanolic-HCl gave cyanidin, $\lambda_{\max}^{EtOH/HCl}$ (nm) 540. It had λ_{\max}^{EtOH} (nm) 280 and ir

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similar to the naturally occurring flavan 3,4-diols and thus could be characterised as leucocyanidin. The other compound was isolated as pale yellow crystalline solid m.p. 314°, $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{EtOH}}$ (nm), 370 and 256.

From the study of spectral shifts^{2,3,4}, ir and its derivatives viz., acetate and methylether it was identified as quercetin.

The residual mother liquor left after extraction with ethylacetate, was concentrated under reduced pressure to a thick brown syrup. The syrup on maceration with hot aq. ethanol (1 : 5 v/v) yielded a colourless substance crystallising as rectangular plates, m.p. 246° (d), $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{EtOH}}$ (nm), 250. On acid hydrolysis it gave ellagic acid and glucose. Quantitative hydrolysis indicated that the compound is a diglucoside. Complete methylation of the glucoside followed by acid hydrolysis gave 3,3', 4'-trimethyl-ether of ellagic acid, m.p. 287° (lit 288°)⁵ which suggested the sugar linkage at position 4 of ellagic acid. Complete hydrolysis of the glycoside with emulsin⁶ and quantitative periodate oxidation⁷ of its methyl ether confirmed it as ellagic acid 4-O- β -gentiobioside (amritoside). This has been reported earlier in the stem bark¹ and leaves⁸ of this plant.

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Chemical Constituents of *Borreria stricta* Linn.

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BORRERIA *stricta* Linn. (N.O. Rubiaceae)
commonly grows in Bundelkhand, upper gangetic

regions, in wastelands, in uncultivated fields and on crevices of rocks¹. No reference on its chemical constituents was available in literature, although sister species have been chemically investigated²⁻⁸. In view of wide availability of this plant, its chemical investigation was carried out to assess its potential as livestock feed and toxic constituents, if any. A systematic chemical investigation revealed the presence of *n*-hexacosanol, palmitic acid, free β -sitosterol, β -D-glucoside of β -sitosterol, ursolic acid, astragalol, rutin, free quercetin, two unidentified triterpenic acids and potassium oxalate. The presence of mannitol, galactose and glucose was detected in aqueous extract. The identity of all the compounds characterized, has been established by direct comparison with the respective authentic samples.

Experimental

The shade dried leaves were found to contain crude protein 10.4%, calcium 0.22% and phosphorus 0.14%. Powdered leaves (6 kg) were exhaustively extracted with 95% alcohol by cold percolation and solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The extractive was separated into petroleum ether and ethylacetate soluble fractions. Both the fractions were chromatographed over Brockmann's neutral alumina and silica gel columns respectively, which yielded following crystalline compounds.

Petroleum ether extract : On keeping deposited a residue which was filtered off. It separated into two crystalline triterpenic acids A & B, on fractionation with aqueous potassium hydroxide.

***n*-Hexacosanol** : Petroleum ether eluted fractions furnished *n*-hexacosanol, crystallised from acetone as colourless crystals m.p. 76-77° (Lit. 79°)⁴. Its acetate melted at 64°.

Palmitic acid : Appeared in the benzene eluted fractions, was crystallised from methanol m.p. 62°.

β -Sitosterol : Which came in acetone fraction, crystallised from chloroform-methanol as shining needles, m.p. and m.m.p. 136-137° (Lit. 136°)⁸, (α)_D²⁰ -33°, acetate, m.p. 129° (α)_D²⁰ -36°.

β -D-glucoside of β -sitosterol : (Ethanol) obtained as white deposition, which crystallised from excess of ethanol, (Charcoal) m.p. 265-68° ; (α)_D²⁰ -36.2°. On hydrolysis (alc., 7% HCl), it yielded β -sitosterol and glucose. It formed an acetate m.p. 178-79°.

Ursolic acid : Obtained from ethyl acetate fraction as shining needles 284-86° (Lit. 285-86°)⁵, (α)_D²¹ +64°, gave an acetate crystallised from acetone as colourless needles m.p. 290-91° (Lit. 293-94°)⁵. The methyl ester (diazomethane) and methyl ester acetate melted at 172-73° (Lit. 169°)⁵ and 243-45° (Lit. 245°)⁵ respectively.